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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Colorectal cancer is the third most common cancer and mostly spreads to liver and lung. Isolated bone metastases are rare and associated with progressed disease.

Case Presentation: A 37-year-old female who was diagnosed with rectal adenocarcinoma developed bone metastasis to clavicle and thoracic vertebra during follow-up. A palliative radiotherapy was applied, but she deceased within 10 months.

Discussion: Young age of patient and absence of an organ metastasis do not eliminate the risk of bone metastasis.

Conclusion: Anamnesis and whole-body examination are important at the time of diagnosis and during the follow-up. It must be considered that bone metastasis may develop at any time.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Young adult, colorectal neoplasms, bone metastasis, pathologic fracture

INTRODUCTION

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is the third most common cancer in men and women (Siegel, Miller, & Jemal, 2019). Distant metastasis is most commonly observed in the liver and lungs, while bone metastases are rare. Isolated bone metastases are even rarer and are generally associated with advanced disease. This case report presents unexpected clavicle metastasis in a young female patient diagnosed with primary CRC without any other distant metastases.

CASE PRESENTATION

Palliative intersphincteric rectal resection and anastomosis were performed to eliminate rectal obstruction that developed during follow-up. Histologic examination of the specimen revealed mucinous adenocarcinoma. Metastases were found in 6 of the 11 removed lymph nodes. The surgical margin was positive on the ventral side of the rectum with perirectal adipose tissue invasion and perinodal spread. Postoperatively, the patient received capecitabine and oxaliplatin chemotherapy and additional radiotherapy for bone metastases. FDG PET-CT performed nine months after the initial diagnosis revealed widespread skeletal metastases and sub-

centimetric metastases in the right lung. The patient died 10 months after the first detection of bone metastasis and 12 months after the initial diagnosis.

DISCUSSION

CRC is one of the most common fatal cancers in the world (Siegel, Miller, & Jemal, 2019). Although metastases are often observed in liver and lungs, bone metastasis is a rare condition and occurs in advanced stages (2 -6%) (Besbeas & Stearns, 1978; Hsu & Wu, 2021). Katoh et al. examined the autopsy results of CRC patients and reported a bone metastasis rate of 23% in 118 patients (Katoh et al., 1995). Bone metastases frequently occurred in the vertebrae, sternum, and ribs, and there were no cases of isolated bone metastasis (Katoh et al., 1995). Bonheim et al. reported the rate of bone metastasis was 4% and the rate of isolated bone metastasis was 1.3% in 1406 cases (Bonnheim, Petrelli, Herrera, et al., 1986). Bone metastasis occurs via the Batson venous plexus and usually appears in the vertebrae, pelvis, sacrum, skull, ribs, femur and humerus (Batson, 1940; Hsu & Wu, 2021; Katoh et al., 1995; Nozue et al., 2002). Some cases were reported with unusual areas of bone metastases such as the mandible, scapula and phalanx (Anoop et al., 2010; Onesti et al., 2011; Sheen et al., 2002;).

To the best of our knowledge, there are only three previously reported cases of CRC that metastasized to the clavicle. One of them involved a 92-year-old woman with additional metastases in the lung and adrenal gland (Doughan, Bennett, & Sagias, 2013). Another case involved a 68-year-old male patient who had a 5-cm mass in the right clavicle and a mass in the left colon (Patel et al., 2007). The third case involved a 67-year-old male who underwent hemicolectomy and hemihepatectomy due to a synchronous hepatic metastasis to the right colon and developed metastases in the left clavicle, pelvis and vertebrae after one year (Sheen, Drake, Langton, et al., 2002).

The prominent feature of our case was skeletal metastasis to an atypical region in a young patient without any other organ involvement. Isolated bone metastasis in primary CRC is extremely rare (less than 2%) (Bonnheim et al., 1986; Nozue et al., 2002). In a study by Roth et al. PET-CT images performed on 252 primary CRC patients with metastases were reevaluated, patients with bone metastasis were reported to have necessarily accompanying lung or liver involvement, and there were no cases of isolated bone metastasis (Roth et al., 2009). In contrast, there was no organ metastasis on the PET-CTs initially performed in our study.

In the literature, survival is poor after bone metastasis in patients with colorectal adenocarcinoma (6-13 months) (Besbeas & Stearns, 1978; Bonnheim et al., 1986; Nozue et al., 2002). In a study by Bonheim et al., the main duration of survival of patients with isolated bone metastasis (10 months) was longer than that of patients with bone and other organ metastases (6 months) (Bonnheim, Petrelli, Herrera, et al., 1986). Similarly, the duration of survival for the patient in our case was 9 months after the first detection of bone metastasis.

Bone involvement is a finding of advanced disease in patients with CRC and the treatment is mostly palliative (Besbeas & Stearns, 1978; Bonnheim et al., 1986; Hsu & Wu, 2021). Radiotherapy is currently the most preferred method for pain relief in patients with CRC. McDonald et al. found a significant increase in quality of life in the early period with single dose radiotherapy in their study of 298 cancer patients with bone involvement (McDonald, Ding, Brundage, et al., 2017). They emphasized that radiotherapy should be offered even to those with a limited expected survival duration (McDonald, Ding, Brundage, et al., 2017). Surgical resection of bony metastasis from CRC may be performed in cases with a solitary metastasis (Onesti et al., 2011). In our case, there was additional involvement in the 10th thoracic vertebral body. Therefore, palliative radiotherapy was used instead of surgical resection. Patients with bone involvement may develop multiple problems that may adversely affect their quality of life, such as pathological fractures, severe bone pain, spinal cord compression and hypercalcemia (Chengling et al., 2021). Determination of the presence of bone metastasis in early stages of the disease is important, especially in younger patients, to improve prognosis so that planned treatment can be performed in a timely fashion (Nozue et al., 2002).

CONCLUSION

This case report presents a phenomenon of a non-metastatic CRC with an isolated bone metastasis that occurred shortly after the diagnosis, which normally rarely poses a problem for patients with bone involvement. Young age of the patient and an absence of a distant organ metastasis should not mean that there is going to be no bone metastasis. In conclusion, anamnesis and whole-body examination are important at the

time of diagnosis and follow-up of the patients, and it should be kept in mind that bone metastasis may develop at any time.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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